

VIPERLAB

FULLY CONNECTED VIRTUAL AND PHYSICAL
PEROVSKITE PHOTOVOLTAICS LAB

**D9.9 Guidelines for electrical
performance measurement of
perovskite PV technology –
main outcomes and final conclusions**

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D9.9. GUIDELINES FOR ELECTRICAL PERFORMANCE MEASUREMENT OF PEROVSKITE PV TECHNOLOGY – MAIN OUTCOMES AND FINAL CONCLUSIONS

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report is part of Work Package 9 of the VIPERLAB project, which aims to enhance and standardize European infrastructure for measurement procedures and best practices related to aging protocols and encapsulation in perovskite photovoltaic (PV) technology.

A key challenge in this field is improving the comparability of electrical performance measurements across laboratories. Factors such as perovskite cell stability, pre-conditioning procedures, and hysteresis in voltage sweep measurements need to be addressed. To address these challenges, the VIPERLAB project organized three Round Robin sample exchanges, focusing on both single-junction and tandem silicon-perovskite devices.

The main objective of this report is to present the results of these intercomparison exercises and provide guidelines to improve the accuracy of performance measurements for perovskite PV technologies. These guidelines align with IEC 60904-1 and IEC 60904-1-1 standards for photovoltaic device measurements and include specific recommendations for single-junction and tandem cells, electrical contact reliability, measurement mask positioning, and temperature control.

Key recommendations include:

- Ensuring appropriate spectral distribution for tandem and single-junction cells.
- Utilizing robust electrical contacts and well-designed sample holders to enhance repeatability.
- Implementing optimal scan speeds for accurate measurements.
- Include precise temperature control of the samples.
- Prioritizing stable cell designs to ensure reliable inter-laboratory comparisons.
- Expanding the number of cells in intercomparison exercises to improve statistical reliability.

While the Round Robin exercises revealed variability across laboratories, the findings underscore the need for standardized protocols to bridge gaps between laboratory and real-world performance conditions. This report provides a critical step forward in advancing the accuracy and reliability of perovskite PV measurement practices, contributing to the broader development of this promising renewable energy technology.

1. INTRODUCTION

This report is part of the Work Package 9 of the VIPERLAB project, the main objective of which is to strengthen and improve the quality of the European infrastructure in the field of measurement procedures and best practices regarding aging protocols and encapsulation in the field of perovskite PV.

In relation to the electrical performance measurements, there are some aspects that need to be addressed to improve the comparability of the results obtained in different laboratories. Those aspects include the stability of the perovskite cell itself, the pre-conditioning procedure applied and the hysteresis between forward and reverse measurements (voltage sweep rate and direction). In order to align the measurement procedures between different laboratories, three Round Robin sample exchanges have been organized during the project.

The objective of this report is to present the main results obtained from those intercomparison exercises and to provide some guidelines to improve the accuracy of the performance measurements of perovskite PV technology, both single junction and tandem devices.

2. ORGANIZATION OF INTERCOMPARISONS

During VIPERLAB project, three round robins have been organized in order to compare the electrical parameters of perovskite cells obtained in different laboratories. Measured devices included single junction and tandem silicon-perovskite technologies, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Summary of the performance round robins organized during Viperlab project.

2.1 First Round Robin organization

First round robin was carried out between months 6 and 18 of the project. In this case, the intercomparison was made by binomials. Four device manufacturers produced some samples for the intercomparison and measured its own devices before sending them to another partner for characterization (AIT and CENER also participated in the round robin). Manufacturers measured again the samples when received back at their facilities for checking the stability of the devices. Each binomial tried to harmonize the protocols and highlighted differences if necessary. The summary of the binomials is shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Summary of the technologies characterised in the first round robin

Manufacturer	Measurer	Structure
CEA	CENER	Flex NIP, hot vacuum lamination
Fraunhofer	CEA	i. Tandem Si/NIP, not encapsulated ii. Single junction rigid PIN, not encapsulated
TNO	AIT	Rigid PIN, UV glue encapsulation
HZB	Fraunhofer	Rigid PIN, UV glue encapsulation

2.2 Second Round Robin organization

Second round robin was conducted between month 18 and 30 of the project. EPFL manufactured all the samples used in this intercomparison, also providing the holders and masks used during the measurements. Samples were encapsulated with UV cured glue and a thin glass.

The intercomparison was organized following a procedure known as Star-shaped Round Robin. Initially, measurements were conducted at **CENER**. Subsequently, each participating laboratory independently assesses the solar cells, taking one substrate each. Following this distributed analysis, the evaluation cycle returns to CENER, where a final round of measurements is performed. This comprehensive approach, involving multiple participants and iterative measurements, ensures a robust and thorough assessment of perovskite solar cell performance, with CENER acting as a central hub in the evaluation process.

Apart from CENER acting as the central hub, the participating partners in the intercomparison were **AIT, CEA, ENEA, FRAUNHOFER** and **JÜLICH**.

2.3 Third Round Robin organization

The third round robin was carried out during the last year of the VIPERLAB project. This time, UV cured encapsulated tandem Si/Perovskite cells were manufactured in CEA.

The evaluation of perovskite solar cells was initially conducted by **CEA** and then distributed to **Fraunhofer**, **HZB** and **ENEA** for their characterization. Samples from Fraunhofer and ENEA were measured again at CEA for checking the stability of the samples. Finally, one of the samples was sent to **CENER**.

Figure 2. Third Round Robin flowchart.

3. DESCRIPTION OF THE SAMPLES

During the intercomparisons organized in the project, several samples from various manufacturers and different topologies have been used.

3.1. Single junction samples

- **Flexible single junction (NIP) (CEA), First Round Robin**

The solar cells manufactured at CEA were flexible single junction cells, with a n-i-p structure. The process was performed on a 24x17 mm² PET substrate, to form the following stack: PET/ITO/SnO₂/PK(Cs, FA)/PTAA/Au contacts. The perovskite layer was deposited via the spin-coating, to form a 400 nm-thick layer. PK deposited via spin-coating process. Each substrate contained two active cells, with an active surface of 0.33 cm² per cell. Due to the chosen structure, these cells must be illuminated from the backside.

The materials chosen for encapsulation were a 50x50 mm² layer of 3M UBF510 as the backside, and an ionomer film (PV8729D). Ag tape was added to form the contacts, as described in Figure 8. This stack was laminated at 130°C under vacuum.

Figure 3. Layout of the flexible n-i-p cells after encapsulation at CEA.

After encapsulation, the substrates were kept in the dark, in air. They were maintained at 23±3 °C at CENER and at 22±1 °C at CEA but have likely suffered higher temperatures during transportation and the following waiting time.

- **Single junction (Fraunhofer), First Round Robin**

Fraunhofer manufactured semi-transparent perovskite single junction solar cell in the regular p-i-n architecture for the first Round Robin.

The structure was glass/TCO/PTAA/PFN/perovskite/C60/SnOx/TCO. Ag electrodes were used as contacts. The devices were not encapsulated. They were sent and kept under inert atmosphere between the measurements. Only during the measurements, they were exposed to ambient air.

- **Rigid single junction (PIN) (TNO), First Round Robin**

The perovskite solar cell stack consists of glass/ITO/HTL/perovskite/passivation layer/C60/SnOx/ITO/Ag finger in p-i-n configuration were fabricated on 2.5 cm x 2.5 cm substrates at HZB. The HTL, perovskite and passivation layers were deposited via slot die coating. C60 was thermally evaporated and SnOx ETL layer was deposited via atmospheric pressure spatial atomic layer deposition technique. ITO was deposited via RF sputtering and finally the Ag grids were thermally evaporated. The solar cells were encapsulated by laminating a polyolefin and a flexible barrier and using solar tape as feedthroughs.

- **Rigid PIN (PIN) (HZB), First Round Robin**

The perovskite solar cell structure manufactured at HZB were of p-i-n configuration with the layer stack being: glass/ITO/Me-4PACz/perovskite/LiF/C60/SnOx/Cu. The substrate size was 2.5 cm × 2.5 cm with 6 test pixels defined on each substrate. The schematic layout of these test structures is shown in **Error! Reference source not found.**. The self-assembled monolayer, [4-(3,6-Dimethyl-9H-carbazol-9-yl)butyl]phosphonic Acid, short Me-4PACz were deposited by spin-coating from a 1 mM solution in absolute ethanol in a N₂-filled glove box. The perovskite layer was deposited via slot die coating from a FA0.4MA0.6PbI₃ perovskite ink. Thin layers of lithium fluoride, LiF, fullerene, C60, and Cu were thermally evaporated after which a SnOx electron transport layer (ETL) was deposited via atomic layer deposition. The solar cells were encapsulated with cavity glass using epoxy glue [1]. These devices were measured under 1 sun illumination using a metallic shadow mask (with active area of 0.09 cm²) at HZB. Before delivery to Fraunhofer ISE, the solar cell devices were stored in a glove box. The samples were packaged in vacuum-sealed plastic bags for shipment to Fraunhofer ISE for measurement.

Figure 4. Layout of p-i-n perovskite solar cell on rigid substrate prepared at HZB. Image from reference [1].

- **Rigid PIN (PIN) (EPFL), Second Round Robin**

The design of perovskite solar cells supplied by EPFL is described below:

Figure 5. Front and rear view of perovskite solar cells supplied by EPFL.

The solar cells were supplied on glass substrates. Each substrate with a size of 2.5 cm x 2.5 cm contained 6 individual solar cells of pixel size 0.2 cm x 0.4 cm = 0.08 cm². Also, the cell electrodes were accessible through a central common (cathode) pad and small metal pads adjacent to each of the cells (anode).

In addition to the cells, EPFL also supplied cables and substrate holders to facilitate making contacts with the cells. Finally, masks were also supplied which left only the pixels area open.

Figure 6. Cable (left), substrate holder (centre) and mask (right) supplied by EPFL.

3.2. Tandem samples

- **Tandem (Fraunhofer), First Round Robin**

Fraunhofer also manufactured monolithic perovskite silicon tandem solar cells for the first Round Robin. The bottom solar cell was a silicon heterojunction solar cell with selective contacts made from doped amorphous silicon. The rear side was textured, the front side was planar. A similar perovskite solar cell architecture as in the single junction device (see 3.1) was used (2PACz instead of PTAA/PFN as hole contact). The cells were sent and kept under inert atmosphere between the measurements. Only during the measurements, they were exposed to ambient air.

- **Tandem (CEA), Third Round Robin**

The third round robin involved solely perovskite – silicon tandem solar cells. The design of the cells supplied by CEA is described in Figure 7:

Figure 7. (Left) Scheme of perovskite-silicon tandem solar cell architecture and (right) front and rear view of tandem solar cells supplied by CEA.

The solar cells encompass a p-i-n perovskite solar cell with a heterojunction silicon solar cell in two terminals configuration, having an active area of 8.88 cm². These photovoltaic solar cells feature a glass/glass encapsulation with dimensions of 80 x 80 mm. For sealing, two types of encapsulation materials were used: UV-polymerizable epoxy glue. Last, for electrical connectivity, the cells use 3M conductive tapes as connectors.

4. ROUND ROBINS WITH SINGLE JUNCTION

4.1. Used protocols

As in the first Round Robin the organization were made by binomials, the measurement protocols were adjusted considering the capabilities of each laboratory, as well as the characteristics of the produced samples. Therefore, four different protocols were used. However, three of them shared the same structure:

- A first phase with several (from 2 to 5) reverse and forward voltage sweeps.
- A second phase with irradiance exposure (from 1 to 3 minutes), in Maximum Power Point Tracking or at a fixed voltage close to V_{MP} .
- The last phase with reverse and forward voltage sweeps.

The fourth protocol used in the first Round Robin only applied the first phase, with three forward and reverse voltage sweeps.

In the second Round Robin, in which all the laboratories measured the same cell design, a single protocol was agreed by the partners, shown in Figure 8. The third step was done by tracking the maximum power point or by monitoring the current at a fixed voltage close to V_{MP} .

Figure 8. Protocol used to determine performance of single junction perovskite cells in the second Round Robin.

4.2. Main results of the First Round Robin with single junction

- **First Round Robin with single junction: CEA – CENER**

Three substrates with two cells each were used in this Round Robin. One of the substrates was not measured in CENER but was used only to determine the effect of the shipping and some cells could not be measured in CENER due to contacting issues.

The evolution of the sample that was not measured in CENER showed an important decrease in its efficiency measured in CEA, using the same protocol and equipment, of more than 20% from the initial value. That seems to be related to the lack of long-term stability of the samples, so no important conclusions about the used protocol could be extracted.

Figure 9. Main electrical parameters obtained during the intercomparison between CEA and CENER.

- **First Round Robin with single junction: FRAUNHOFER – CEA**

One substrate with three working individual semi-transparent perovskite cells was used in this intercomparison. Initially the cells were measured in Fraunhofer, were sent to CEA and went back to Fraunhofer for checking their stability.

From the initial and final measurements in Fraunhofer, it was seen that the cells were quite stable, only a slight improvement of the solar cells was observed.

Differences between the initial measurement in Fraunhofer and CEA were in the range of 2% in PCE. The discrepancies came mostly from the short circuit current. As the cells were semi-

transparent and there were reflections from the measurement table in CEA, it was assumed that the cause of the differences could be due to those reflections.

Figure 10. Main electrical parameters obtained during the intercomparison between FRAUNHOFER and CEA.

- **First Round Robin with single junction: HZB – FRAUNHOFER**

Six cells were used in the intercomparison between HZB and Fraunhofer in the first Round Robin exercise. The cells were measured initially and finally in HZB to check their stability. In general, the short circuit current decreases but the open circuit voltage increases, resulting in a total variation in PCE below 1%.

As shown in Figure 11, the results obtained in the PCE in HZB and Fraunhofer are in good agreement, with differences in the range of 1-2% in PCE.

Figure 11. Main electrical parameters obtained during the intercomparison between HZB and FRAUNHOFER.

- **First Round Robin with single junction: TNO – AIT**

As mentioned before, the protocol used in the intercomparison between TNO and AIT was different from those used in the other intercomparisons. In this case there was no Maximum Power Point Tracking of the cells for some minutes, only forward and reverse voltage sweeps have been applied.

Figure 12. Comparison of the PV parameters measured. Full symbols represent the reverse scan values, while the empty ones represent the forward scan values. Figure 12 shows the electrical parameters obtained during the second J-V scans. In general, the samples during the intercomparison increase their J_{SC} , in turn increasing the PCE as measured in TNO. Difference in PCE between the initial measurement in TNO and AIT is in the range of 1-2%, mainly caused by the V_{oc} value.

An interesting point related with the protocol used is the hysteresis calculated in the laboratories. In TNO there are more differences between the reverse and forward voltage sweeps, although the voltage sweep is just slightly slower in AIT (175 mV/s instead of 200 mV/s).

Figure 12. Comparison of the PV parameters measured. Full symbols represent the reverse scan values, while the empty ones represent the forward scan values.

4.3. Main results from the Second Round Robin with single junction

An important aspect for knowing the validity of the intercomparison results is the stability of the samples along the whole process. To check it, the samples measured in the different laboratories were measured again at CENER.

The following figure shows the initial and final measurements in CENER. All of them were performed using the same equipment and following the same protocol. The results of two cells that had been stored at CENER are also included.

Figure 13. Stability of the samples measured at the beginning and the end of the Round Robin.

As it can be seen in the figure, the short circuit current is heavily influenced by the measurements. Open circuit voltage is also slightly influenced, and fill factor seems to be stable (although silver paste had to be added to some of the substrates). As a result, maximum power is affected by the measurements. Values of the cells stored in CENER seem to be more stable. This variability could affect the extraction of reliable conclusions during the intercomparison process.

Additionally, hysteresis was assessed throughout the protocol, incorporating a fourth reverse-forward sweep with an increased delay time of 50 ms for acquiring each point in the I-V curve, compared to the 20 ms used in the first three voltage sweeps. This value was calculated by the following equation:

$$Hyst = \frac{P_{max_rev} - P_{max_fwd}}{P_{max_fwd}}$$

The hysteresis for each step of the protocol is shown in the following image:

Figure 14. Hysteresis along the test protocol.

From the graph, increasing the delay time to 50 ms has not caused a reduction in the hysteresis detected with the used solar cells. According to the data obtained, the second sweeps (just before the MPPT exposure) had the lowest hysteresis. Regarding the maximum power, P_{max} , throughout the protocol steps, its progression is depicted in Figure 15.

Figure 15. Evolution of the maximum power (P_{max}) along the steps of the measurement protocol.

Although higher values of Pmax are observed in the forward I-V curve compared to the reverse one, no significant variation in Pmax is evident as the protocol progresses.

The normalized external quantum efficiency of the perovskite solar cells was also measured during the round robin, showing good consistency across measurements conducted in different laboratories.

Figure 16. Averaged normalized EQE obtained among the different labs.

- **Second Round Robin: CENER – FRAUNHOFER**

The following image shows the electrical parameters measured initially in CENER, in Fraunhofer, and finally in CENER. The values obtained during the third reverse I-V curve (after the three minutes exposure) are shown in Fig. 17.

Adding silver paste to the cell connections facilitated the measurements, enabling the evaluation of some cells that initially could not be measured and improving the Fill Factor (*FF*) by enhancing the quality of the electrical connections. Difference in maximum power ranges from -5.6% to 2.5% and open circuit voltage has the lowest difference.

Figure 17. Comparison of the results between Fraunhofer and CENER.

- **Second Round Robin with single junction: CENER – JÜLICH**

The next figure shows the electrical parameters measured initially and finally at CENER, and the measurement at Jülich. Data presented correspond to the third reverse I-V curve.

Figure 18. Comparison of the results between Jülich and CENER.

There is a significant difference in short-circuit current, exceeding 6% for all pixels, which is the main factor driving variations in maximum power. Potential causes for these differences include aspects related to the irradiance received by the cells, such as mask positioning and spectral adjustments.

- **Second Round Robin with single junction: CENER – AIT**

The following image shows the electrical parameters of the four pixels measured at AIT and CENER:

Figure 19. Comparison of the results between AIT and CENER.

Differences in maximum power are primarily attributed to variations in Fill Factor and short-circuit current, suggesting potential issues with the electrical connections of the cells and the irradiance received, which could be influenced by factors such as mask positioning, irradiance adjustments, and spectral distribution.

- **Second Round Robin with single junction: CENER – CEA**

The following image shows the electrical parameters measured in CENER and CEA.

Figure 20. Comparison of the results between CEA and CENER.

While some cells exhibit differences of less than 2% in maximum power, others show higher differences, possibly due to inherent instability of the cells or connection issues. Upon returning the cells to CENER, the maximum power was lower than the initial values, indicating sample degradation during the Round Robin process.

- **Second Round Robin with single junction: CENER – ENEA**

Four pixels were measured initially at CENER before sending the substrate to ENEA. As there were electrical contact failures there, silver paste was applied on the device pads; so finally, five of the cells were measured at ENEA. However, only three of the pixels could be characterized at both laboratories. Their results are presented in the following image:

Figure 21. Comparison of the results between ENEA and CENER.

Significant differences in Fill Factor were likely caused by connection issues, and a clear degradation in short-circuit current was observed during the Round Robin process.

4.4. Conclusions from the two Round Robins with single junction

Degradation of the samples affected the measurements, even to the meta-stability effects occurring during preconditioning.

The spectral distribution of the light source also affected the results. For single junction cells this effect can be minimized by using a spectral mismatch correction.

Positioning of the measurement mask is also important to avoid differences. The reflections of the measurement table for semi-transparent solar cells may cause deviations in the determination of J_{SC} .

Fill Factor is mainly affected by the connecting system between the cell terminals and the electronic load. V_{oc} is affected by the sample temperature, so it is also important to use a temperature probe in order to correct the electrical parameters to STC.

Encapsulated single junction perovskite solar cells delivered with substrate holders, wires, and masks reduced the sources of uncertainty in the measurements performed in the different measurement laboratories in these two aspects: aperture area and connection procedure.

The protocol used in the second round robin to determine performance consisting of nine steps (Figure 8, single junction), showed no significant variation or trend in the main electrical parameters at the different steps.

During the initial measurements of the second round robin, increasing the delay time from 20 ms to 50 ms did not lead to a reduction in hysteresis, with the lowest hysteresis observed in the second reverse and forward scan.

Discrepancies have been detected in short circuit current that could be related to differences in irradiance among labs: mask positioning, irradiance adjustment, spectral distribution...

Differences are smaller for those cells which seem to be stable.

Comparing measurements of the second round robin, before and after their shipment to the measuring labs, the short circuit current has been heavily influenced by the measurements. Open circuit voltage has been also slightly influenced. The mean value for the fill factor seems to be stable (although silver paste had to be added to some of the substrates), but there are several samples in which the FF is different between labs. As a result, maximum power is affected by the measurements.

5. ROUND ROBINS WITH TANDEMS

5.1. Used protocols

The first round robin included a binomial in which tandem cells manufactured by Fraunhofer were characterised. The measurement protocol included initially two forward and reverse voltage sweeps, followed by a fixed voltage tracking during 60 to 90 seconds and a final forward and reverse voltage sweeps.

In this case there was an important difference in the sun simulator used. Fraunhofer used a simulator with two different lamps for adjusting the spectral distribution, while CEA used a sun simulator with only a Xenon lamp.

In the third round robin CEA – the cell manufacturer – proposed a protocol starting with Maximum Power Tracking during 3 minutes, followed by a reverse and forward voltage sweeps and a last step with a faster reverse and forward voltage sweeps. ENEA replicated the same protocol.

Fraunhofer and CENER modified slightly the measurement protocol. Instead of starting with MPPT, reverse and forward voltage sweeps were done to extract the V_{MP} , and the cells were exposed at that voltage while irradiated.

HZB used a different protocol, including several reverse and forward voltage sweeps, Maximum Power Point Tracking during 3 minutes and final reverse and forward voltage sweeps.

The protocols applied are summarized in Figure 22.

Figure 22. Protocols used to determine **performance** of tandem perovskite-Si solar cells in RR3.

These protocols were designed to evaluate the performance of tandem solar cells through a series of controlled tests under varying illumination spectrum conditions. The cells are tested under continuous 1 sun illumination with the AM1.5 solar spectrum, simulating standard sunlight exposure. This includes maximum power point tracking (MPPT) and fixed voltage measurements to track stability and efficiency over time and a range of IV scans performed in both forward and reverse directions. These IV scans are conducted at different speeds, categorized as slow and fast, to capture dynamic performance metrics. Additionally, extended IV scans are included to provide a more comprehensive view of the cell’s response.

Temperature control is also a crucial part of these protocols, as maintaining or varying temperature conditions during measurements causes differences in the results.

Finally, the illumination equipment most used among the partners are LED-based solar simulators, except CENER, which uses a Xenon lamp with an additional 940 nm IR LED to reduce the mismatch factor and achieve a more accurate IV curve measurement for tandem cells.

The protocol agreed by the partners to determine the quantum efficiency (QE) of the perovskite tandem solar cells under study was based on the standard IEC 60904-8-1: Photovoltaic devices –

Part 8-1: Measurement of spectral responsivity of multi-junction photovoltaic devices and the publication of Meusel et al (2003).

5.2. Main results of the Round Robins with tandem

• First Round Robin with tandem: FRAUNHOFER – CEA

Two tandem solar cell substrates (8 individual cells in total) were used for this round robin. A comparison of the solar cell parameters obtained at Fraunhofer before shipping and at CEA can be seen in Figure 23.

Figure 23. Comparison of measurement results of tandem solar cells obtained at CEA and Fraunhofer. JV parameters obtained from best JV curve are shown in each case.

Comparing the results from Fraunhofer and CEA, some clear differences can be seen. The V_{OC} is slightly, and the FF is strongly lower in CEA. While the J_{SC} at Fraunhofer is almost the same for all eight solar cells, there is a large spread in the measurements at CEA.

After sending back the cells to Fraunhofer, they were measured again, and no significant differences were seen. Taking that into account, it seems that part of the discrepancies in FF and J_{SC} could

come from the different spectral conditions. Moreover, misalignment of the shadow mask and contacting issues are also probably affecting the results in J_{SC} and FF respectively.

- **Second Round Robin with tandem: CEA – ENEA – FRAUNHOFER – HZB – CENER**

Three tandem cells manufactured by CEA were used in this Round Robin. As the laboratories used different measurement protocols but all of them included an exposure period of 180 s, the reverse voltage sweep right after that exposure is compared in

Figure 24.

Figure 24. Comparison of measurement results of tandem solar cells obtained during the third RR.

The differences in maximum power relative to the mean value obtained by the laboratories were less than 3% across the three solar cells studied.

The External Quantum Efficiency (EQE) of the tandem solar cells was also evaluated before performing the current-voltage (IV) curve to adjust the solar simulator spectrum accordingly ensuring proper current matching.

Figure 25. Comparison of relative EQE of tandem solar cells obtained during the third RR.

The spectral evaluation shows good agreement among laboratories, with differences of less than 3% observed in the 400–750 nm range for the PSK sub-cell and in the 750–1150 nm range for the Si sub-cell.

5.3. Conclusions from the two Round Robins with tandem

Main conclusions obtained from the intercomparison of tandem cells are shown below:

- The tandem cells evaluated have shown stable behaviour during the round robin measurements and no degradation was observed during the intercomparison process.
- In case tandem cells are included in the round robin, ensure that the spectral distribution is appropriate, minimizing the current mismatch between the junctions. A multi-lamp sun simulator is needed for the adjustment.
- Although there were differences in the measurement protocols used, results from all laboratories showed good agreement.

6. RELIABLE TESTING PROCEDURE FOR ELECTRICAL CHARACTERIZATION OF PEROVSKITE (-SILICON TANDEM) SOLAR CELLS

A main conclusion from the above-mentioned round robins was that a comparison of measurements may be significantly hindered by cell degradation which may partly be attributed to direct contact of

the cell to ambient air. In addition to challenges of comparison of measurement setups this effect may also hinder the study of fundamental cell degradation effects which may occur in addition to air-related degradation effects. For the final application a solar cell is enclosed in a module which shields the cells from the environment such that humidity or oxygen do not interact with the cell as they do under bare cell conditions.

In order to be able to assess both, the accuracy of measurement procedures and the stability of solar cells under operating conditions it is therefore very helpful to establish a lab routine to encapsulate cells before measurement. Several challenges have to be solved for this purpose:

- The optics of the cell under test are affected by the module glass which have to be considered when comparing measurements.
- The electrical performance of the cell may be altered by the encapsulation process itself as the process involves handling, soldering and enhanced temperatures.
- An internal process flow needs to be defined which enables a regular cell processing in a limited time and reasonable effort.

The outcome of the round robins in WP9 suggested to establish suitable procedures for cell analysis in Fraunhofer ISE labs which was realized as follows.

Figure 26. Procedure of perovskite-silicon tandem solar cell processing and encapsulation at Fraunhofer ISE.

Cell processing at Fraunhofer ISE labs is separated in bottom cell processing (Figure 26, left) and a subsequent perovskite top cell processing in a glove-box environment (Figure 26, middle). Glass-glass mini modules are prepared with these cells. Cell contacting consists of 4 wires per cell in order to enable precise 4-point probe measurements for each individual cell (Figure 26, right).

Figure 27. Comparison of measured cell efficiencies in two conditions: as bare cells (green) and encapsulated (orange). Both, reverse and forward scan results are shown.

Figure 27 shows first results of a measurement comparison between bare cell measurements and encapsulated measurements. The following conclusions can be drawn:

- Cells can be measured after the new encapsulation process with comparable efficiencies (see cells #1 and #3).
- Care has to be taken to avoid delayed cell processing which includes longer periods of air exposure prior to encapsulation. Here, a larger difference between cell and module measurements is expected (see cell #9 and #17).
- A larger spread of efficiencies is expected for delayed cell processing with an enhanced risk of cell failure.

In summary the introduction of a measurement routine concept using encapsulated cells for electrical analyses of perovskite-silicon tandem solar cells was successful and will be further developed.

7. MAIN CONCLUSIONS AND GUIDELINES

This report summarises the work that has been carried out throughout the project during the intercomparison exercises. From the information extracted during the performance round robins and the analysis of published existing protocols, described in deliverable D4.6, some **guidelines for electrical measurements of perovskite cells** are provided below.

The guidelines presented below align with the general principles of photovoltaic (PV) device measurement as described in IEC 60904-1 and IEC 60904-1-1, which also can apply to perovskite-based solar cells. Some specific highlights extracted are:

Related to the characteristics of the solar simulators:

- When measuring single junction cells, apply the spectral mismatch factor (SMM) correction as per standard requirements.
- When measuring tandem cells, ensure that the SMM for each junction approaches unity and adjust the spectral distribution of the light source using a multi-lamp sun simulator for accurate characterization.
- Be cautious of reflections, which can affect the accuracy of measurements in semi-transparent devices. Implement measures to account for or reduce these effects.

Contact Reliability:

- Special attention must be given to the quality and reliability of electrical contacts, as inconsistencies can lead to variations in the fill factor (FF).
- The use of well-designed sample holders can enhance the repeatability and reliability of measurements.

Measurement Mask Positioning:

- Proper alignment and positioning of the measurement mask are critical to minimizing measurement artifacts.

Scan Speed Adjustment

- Optimize the scan speed according to the sample under evaluation. While no significant differences were observed in some cases (e.g., during the second round robin), other studies (e.g., first round robin, TNO-AIT) have shown a certain sensitivity to scan rate.

Temperature Monitoring and Control:

- Actively monitor and control the sample temperature during measurements to improve accuracy, especially in open circuit voltage.

Some aspects to consider for the organisation of future round robins are also provided:

Stability of Cells for Intercomparison

- Use stable devices to ensure meaningful comparisons across laboratories. Long-term stability of the cells is essential for robust intercomparison results.
- The development of a reliable testing procedure for the electrical characterization of perovskite-silicon tandem solar cells has proven essential to address challenges related to cell degradation and measurement variability. As shown in Fraunhofer tests, encapsulation prior to testing effectively mitigates air-related degradation effects, aligning testing conditions more closely with real-world applications. Results showed that encapsulated cells achieve comparable efficiencies to bare cells when air exposure is minimized prior to encapsulation. However, delays in processing increase variability and the risk of cell failure.

Cell Size and Measurement Variability:

- Intercomparing larger cells could mitigate inaccuracies caused by variations in mask positioning.

Reference Cell Exchange:

- For consistency in irradiance settings across laboratories, exchanging a reference cell (preferably a filtered silicon cell) is recommended.

Increasing Statistical Significance:

- Expanding the number of cells involved in intercomparison exercises would enhance the statistical reliability of the results.

Steady-State Performance vs. Measurement Conditions

- It is important to note that the differences between laboratory measurements and steady-state outdoor performance conditions were not assessed in these round-robin tests.

REFERENCES

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